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Blind Traveler's Evaluations of Sensory Information Agents at Servicescapes

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Abstract: This study investigated visually disabled customers' expectations about sensory information cues when consuming products and services at travel-related servicescapes. This study collected and analyzed blind travelers' blogs to obtain its objective. The findings help enrich the literature about sensory promotion toward visually disabled customers in the hospitality and tourism context. They also provide insights to offer better information to these special-needs customers.

Keywords: blind travelers, sensory information, servicescape

Introduction

Product and service providers have used many sensory cues to inform customers at their servicescapes, including visual (pictorial and textual) and audio (music and narrative) cues. These cues can influence customers' perceptions and behaviors (Martinez, Neves, & Martinez, 2020; Shaouf, Lü, & Li, 2016).

Unfortunately, visually impaired customers (sensory-disabled customers) may be unable to receive and comprehend the verbal cues and their hidden messages fully. Other cues must be adopted or emphasized in these cases to replace the missing ones. For example, verbal narratives provided via apps and support devices can give visually impaired individuals details about an object or facility (Nair, Olmschenk, Seiple, & Zhu, 2022). Alternatively, Braille brochures, leaflets, or signs can give them

tactile cues for better comprehension (Senjam, Foster, Bascaran, Vashist, & Gupta, 2020). Many promotional activities additionally employ olfactory and gustatory cues (Chambaran, Chisin, Chabanet, Issanchou, & Brand, 2015; Lwin & Morrin, 2012; Meng, Zamudio, & Jewell, 2021). Visually impaired customers, if they do not have other sensory disabilities, may be able to receive the information and messages.

However, providing sufficient information about the potential products and services to visually disabled customers is challenging, mainly when they leave their daily environments to travel (Armour, 2018; Curran, Walters, & Robinson, 2007; Kim, 2021). The power of sensory promotion in improving visually disabled customer's perceptions and triggering their positive reactions has not been utilized (Simmonds, Bogomolova, Kennedy, Nenyecz-Thiel, & Bellman, 2020; Wei, Liu, Xu, Li, & Cao, 2022). Understanding visually disabled customers' preferences for suitable sensory cues in information provision must be the first step in this utilization process.

Therefore, this study investigates visually disabled customers' expectations about sensory information cues when consuming products and services at travel-related servicescapes (Figure 1). The findings help enrich the literature about sensory promotion toward visually disabled customers in the hospitality and tourism context. They also provide insights to offer better information to these special-needs customers.

Figure 1

Sensory Information Cues

Source: author's own development

Method

This study collected and analyzed blind travelers' blogs to obtain its objective. Four prominent blind bloggers were identified via Google Search. Five latest entries per blogger were collected as the data in November 2023 (Table 1).

Table 1

Blog Links and Contexts

Number	Link	Contexts
1	https://www.blindtravels.com/	Accommodation
2	https://www.tonythetraveller.com/	Tourism
3	https://www.blindgirladventures.com/	Cruise
4	https://www.facebook.com/travellingblind/	Travel

Source: author’s own development

The researcher applied the content analysis method to identify the senses the bloggers used to receive the information (Elo & Kyngäs, 2008). They also adopted sentiment analysis to differentiate positive and negative encounters (Liu, 2015).

Results

Blind travelers with weak visual faculties expect proper lighting to help them orient themselves to their surroundings. They also wanted sign boards and menus with large-size words and contrasting colors (Figure 2). These visual cues help enhance their information reception significantly.

Figure 2

Blind Travelers’ Sensory Information Cue Preferences

Source: author’s own development

Blind travelers without any sight ability preferred facilities and boards with Braille signs so they could touch them with their hands (Figure 2). They would also appreciate clear and detailed audio instructions. Noticeably, when human counterparts spoke, the blind travelers expected a not-too-much but not-too-little instruction. When the instruction was automated, they wanted prior notice about generating the instruction, preferably Braille signs. Some blind travelers even used smells to find places (e.g., the swimming pools). Most did not use the sense of taste to orient themselves and navigate the surroundings. Interestingly, the blind travelers had a sense of spatial awareness. They often compared themselves to mobility-disabled individuals regarding this point. They would like decent spaces between objects and wayfinding assistance equipment. Overall, the tactile (including spatial layout), audio, and olfactory cues are helpful for blind travelers when receiving information about or at servicescapes.

Conclusion

As customers, blind travelers want to receive proper information about the products, services, and servicescapes. The providers can adopt the sensory marketing theory to better accommodate these customers' needs. They could create blind-friendly signs (touch), instructions (audio), and layouts (spatial) for their servicescapes. The providers should also adequately train their staff to maximize comfort for those who cannot see and must rely on other senses, such as hearing and touching.

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